

A META-ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF PEER FEEDBACK ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN THE STEM FIELDS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

P.D. Pereira¹

Department of Teacher Development, University of Twente
Enschede, The Netherlands
ORCID: 0000-0001-6355-421X

M.C. Heitink

Cognition, Data and Education, University of Twente
Enschede, The Netherlands
ORCID: 0000-0003-0636-1299

K. Schildkamp

Department of Teacher Development, University of Twente
Enschede, The Netherlands
ORCID: 0000-0001-6154-6857

B.P. Veldkamp

Cognition, Data and Education, University of Twente
Enschede, The Netherlands
0000-0003-3543-2164

R. Feskens

Cognition, Data and Education, University of Twente
Enschede, The Netherlands

¹ *Corresponding Author*

P.D. Pereira

p.d.pereira@utwente.nl

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ABSTRACT

Recently, there has been a significant increase in the use of peer feedback in higher education. However, the evidence of the effect of peer feedback on students' academic achievement does not seem conclusive and, to our knowledge, there has not yet been a meta-analysis of the effect of peer feedback on general academic achievement in the STEM fields of higher education. Therefore, we conducted a meta-analysis to determine whether peer feedback is beneficial to STEM higher education students' academic achievement. The final data set for the meta-analysis consisted of 286 effect sizes from 90 independent samples in 75 studies, with a total of over 14,000 participants. All effect sizes were calculated as Cohen's d values. A random-effects model used to synthesise the effect sizes indicated a significant positive summary effect size ($d = .421$, $SE = .037$, 95% $CI = .350, .493$, $p = .000$). The variance of the true effect sizes (T^2) was .069. The Q_w value of 644.167 was significant ($p = .000$) and the I^2 value of 88.512 was high. Therefore, in order to identify the source of the between-study heterogeneity, moderator analyses were conducted to evaluate the influence of various methodological quality characteristics and peer feedback intervention characteristics on the effect of a peer feedback intervention. The results of this study will provide researchers, policy makers and practitioners with the information they need to decide whether or not to use peer feedback and to be able to design peer feedback interventions for maximal effectiveness.

1 INTRODUCTION

There has been a significant increase in the use of peer feedback in higher education. Peer feedback involves students providing their peers with feedback on their draft work and/or receiving feedback on their own draft work, followed by revising their work based on their peers' work and/or based on the feedback they received [1]. Research on the effect of peer feedback on academic achievement in the STEM fields of higher education found a positive effect (e.g. [2], [3]), a negative effect (e.g. [4], [5]), no effect (e.g. [6], [7]) or a limited effect (e.g. [8]). To come to a consensus on the effect of peer feedback on academic achievement in the STEM fields of higher education, this research used meta-analytic methods to synthesise the available literature to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of a peer feedback intervention on the academic achievement of students in the STEM fields of higher education?
2. How do the peer feedback intervention characteristics moderate the effect of a peer feedback intervention on the academic achievement of students in the STEM fields of higher education?

2 METHODOLOGY

The data collection was based on [9] and was conducted in four steps.

2.1 Determination of Inclusion Criteria

To be included in the meta-analysis, studies should have have:

1. Been published as an English-language article in a peer-reviewed journal
2. Been conducted in the context of a course in STEM higher education
3. Involved the implementation of a formative peer feedback intervention
4. Been designed with a control condition and an intervention condition
5. Included at least 15 participants in each condition
6. Reported quantitative measures of students' academic achievement as the outcome measure

2.2 Search for Literature

To find articles for inclusion in the meta-analysis, three approaches were used: 1) searching through existing meta-analyses on peer feedback, 2) searching through electronic databases, and 3) backward and forward searching using the references and citations of the articles shortlisted from the first two approaches.

First, the articles included in the meta-analysis of the effect of peer feedback on academic writing by [10] were considered. Second, for the search through databases, four databases were selected (ERIC, PsycINFO, Web of Science and Scopus). A search string was created using the keywords 'peer feedback', 'STEM' and 'higher education', along with synonyms for these keywords. Third, once articles were shortlisted from the meta-analysis by [10] and the database search results, all English-language journal articles were identified from: 1) the reference lists of these

articles, and 2) the citations of these articles found on Web of Science, Scopus, ResearchGate and Google Scholar.

2.3 Identification of Studies

This search for literature resulted in a total of 6,935 unique results. The titles and abstracts of these articles were put through a preliminary screening to determine whether the articles satisfied the second and third inclusion criteria, with articles not satisfying either or both of these criteria being excluded. The full manuscripts of the remaining 1,419 articles were sought, and the full manuscripts of the 1,330 articles that could be obtained were then put through a thorough screening using the second, third, fourth, fifth and sixth inclusion criteria. During this screening, 92 articles were selected for data extraction.

2.4 Data Extraction from Studies

An extensive data extraction form was created to obtain the data from the selected articles. Data from all articles was extracted and coded by two researchers. The two researchers' codes were compared to ensure reliability of coding procedures and decisions. Any discrepancies in the codes were discussed by the two researchers until a consensus was reached. Also, any doubts were clarified through discussion with a third researcher and/or a statistics expert. Some of the articles contained data for multiple effect sizes, resulting in a total of 367 effect sizes from the 92 articles.

3 DATA ANALYSIS

The data analysis was based on [11], using Comprehensive Meta-Analysis.

3.1 Summary Effect Size

In the case of studies with a pre-test post-test design, the pre-test results were compared with the post-test results. In the case of studies with a controlled trial design, the post-test results for the control group were compared with the post-test results for the intervention condition. In the few cases where a pre-test was conducted just before the peer feedback activity, the difference between the pre-test and post-test results for the control group was compared with the difference between the pre-test and post-test results for the intervention group. The individual effect sizes were computed as Cohen's d values.

Ultimately, of the 367 effect sizes, 30 could not be calculated and were excluded from the meta-analysis. Moreover, some of the effect sizes were not included in our final analyses, e.g., to include only mutually exclusive effect sizes within articles, to exclude articles that reported the same study and same effect size(s) as another article, and to exclude articles with extreme effect sizes. In order to avoid inflating the sample size, an overall effect size was computed for each study, and each study contributed only this one overall effect size to the meta-analysis. The final data set for the meta-analysis consisted of 286 effect sizes from 90 independent samples in 75 studies, with a total of over 14,000 participants.

A random-effects model was used to compute the summary effect size. Using the model, the summary effect size (d) as well as the standard error (SE), 95% confidence interval (CI) and significance (p) of the summary effect size were computed. For the summary effect size, significance was set at $p < .05$.

3.2 Between-Study Heterogeneity of the True Effect Sizes

To check for the between-study heterogeneity of the true effect sizes, the variance of the true effect sizes between studies (T^2) was computed. In addition, a measure of whether the observed variance was significantly different from that expected from within-study variance alone (Q_w) and a measure of the proportion of the observed variance that was from the variance of the true effect sizes (I^2) were computed. For the Q_w value, significance was set at $p < .05$. For the I^2 value, 25%, 50% and 75% were considered low, moderate and high heterogeneity, respectively [12]. If the Q_w value was significant and the I^2 value was high, moderator analyses would be justified [12].

3.3 Moderating Effects of Methodological Quality Characteristics

Methodological quality characteristics could have a moderating effect on the effectiveness of a peer feedback intervention. If the moderating effect is significant, caution should be exercised when combining studies with different attributes of the characteristic. Therefore, a series of moderator analyses were conducted to check for the moderating effect of pre-selected methodological quality characteristics.

3.4 Moderating Effects of Peer Feedback Intervention Characteristics

Peer feedback intervention characteristics could also have a moderating effect on the effectiveness of a peer feedback intervention. If the moderating effect is significant, it could help to explain the between-study heterogeneity of the true effect sizes. Therefore, a series of moderator analyses were conducted to check for the moderating effect of pre-selected peer feedback intervention characteristics.

A mixed-effects model was used to conduct each moderator analysis independently of the other moderator analyses. Using the model, a measure of whether the observed variance across the attributes of the characteristic was significantly different from that expected from within-study variance alone (Q_b) was computed. For the Q_b value, significance was set at $p < .01$.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Summary Effect Size

The meta-analysis revealed a significant positive summary effect size of peer feedback on academic achievement ($n = 286$, $k = 75$, $d = .421$, $SE = .037$, $CI = .350$, $.493$, $p = .000$), representing a medium effect size [13].

4.2 Between-Study Heterogeneity of the True Effect Sizes

The variance of the true effect sizes (T^2) was .069. The Q_w value of 644.167 was significant ($p = .000$), indicating that the true effect sizes in the primary studies were

not the same, while the I^2 value of 88.512 was high, indicating that the proportion of true variance to observed variance was high. Since the Q_w value was significant and the I^2 value was high, moderator analyses were conducted to attempt to identify the source of the between-study heterogeneity.

4.3 Moderating Effects of Methodological Quality Characteristics

Moderator analyses were conducted to check for the moderating effect of the research design used in the study, the type of allocation used to create groups, the equivalence between the groups created and the blinding of the assessor(s) to the condition of the participants. For each of the analyses, the Q_b value was not significant. Since there was no evidence that the methodological quality characteristics had a moderating effect, it was deemed appropriate to combine studies with different attributes of the characteristics in a single meta-analysis.

4.4 Moderating Effects of Peer Feedback Intervention Characteristics

Moderator analyses were also conducted to check for the moderating effect of a range of peer feedback intervention characteristics, with respect to the nature of the task subjected to peer feedback, the nature of the peer feedback itself, the logistics of the peer feedback activity, the support for the peer feedback activity and the grading associated with the peer feedback activity. For each of the analyses, the Q_b value was not significant.

5 CONCLUSION

The meta-analysis showed that peer feedback is beneficial for improving academic achievement in the STEM fields of higher education. Therefore, it is recommended that peer feedback be incorporated in courses, where possible and appropriate.

It was hoped that the results of this study would provide the data needed to be able to design peer feedback interventions for maximal effectiveness. The way a peer feedback intervention is implemented can vary widely, and it can be presumed that the way in which it is implemented can influence the extent to which a peer feedback intervention is effective. While the moderator analyses in this study did not show a significant moderating effect of any of the peer feedback intervention characteristics tested, it does not rule out the possibility that (at least some of) these characteristics can make a difference. As explained by [14], moderator analyses are often insignificant and insignificant findings do not always mean that the characteristic does not have an influence on the effect. Therefore, it is recommended that, when designing a peer feedback activity, consideration is given to which design characteristics are likely to increase students' participation in the activity, elicit feedback of high quantity and quality and improve students' use of and learning from the feedback they provide and receive. It is also recommended that further research be conducted to increase the knowledge on how a peer feedback intervention can be designed for maximal effectiveness.

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